

Education Quarterly Reviews

Ansyah, Edi, Wachidi, and Riyanto. (2021), The Effect of Learning Methods and Cognitive Style on Student Learning Achievement. In: *Education Quarterly Reviews*, Vol.4, No.4, 79-85.

ISSN 2621-5799

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1993.04.04.372

The online version of this article can be found at:
<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

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The Effect of Learning Methods and Cognitive Style on Student Learning Achievement

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to examine: The effect of discussion and recitation methods on learning achievement, the effect of independent and dependent cognitive styles on learning achievement, the interaction between learning methods and cognitive style on learning achievement, whether learning achievement by using the discussion method with independent cognitive style was higher than the recitation learning method, whether learning achievement using the discussion method with a dependent cognitive style was higher than the recitation method. This research used quantitative research methods, the type of research was quasi-experimental factorial 2x2 with a population of 173 students and the sample was 61 students. The data collection technique used was a test of cognitive style and learning achievement. The analysis technique used two way ANOVA test and t-test. The results of hypothesis testing concluded: There was an influence of discussion learning methods and recitation learning methods on learning achievement, there was an influence of cognitive style on learning achievement, there was an interaction between learning methods and cognitive styles on student learning achievement, learning achievement using the discussion method of students who had independent cognitive style was higher than the dependent, learning achievement using the recitation method of students who had an independent cognitive style was not higher than the independent.

Keywords: Learning method, Cognitive Style, Learning Achievement

1. Introduction

The problems that exist in Islamic Religious Universities (PTAI) both public and private, especially IAIN Bengkulu, especially in the Tarbiyah and Tadris Faculty of Islamic Religious Education (PAI) study programs are still the low quality of learning, this causes students to be less fully involved in learning, students are not motivated to develop thinking skills, learning does not give meaning to students and the low learning achievement achieved. Effective learning prioritizes student involvement in learning so that they receive, process and store information more optimally and make learning more meaningful.

The research methodology course is a compulsory subject for students in every faculty and study program at IAIN Bengkulu, which is a provision for students to compile scientific works (thesis) in completing studies. In fact, this course does not provide students with provisions and abilities, this is because students in lectures are not maximally active (come, sit, silent), so that students' ability to understand lecture material is not maximally achieved, students think this course is not so important, low learning motivation, students lack confidence, besides that students' thinking skills in receiving, managing, and storing information are not managed properly this will have an impact on the achievements achieved by students. Learning achievement is a measure of the success of a learning process, student achievement reflects the level of mastery and ability of the material being taught. In addition to student problems, learning cannot be separated from the role of lecturers who carry out learning. The role of the lecturer or teacher is a facilitator or moderator. Its job is to stimulate, help students to want to learn on their own and formulate their knowledge. The lecturer also evaluates whether the student's ideas are in accordance with the ideas of the experts or not. While the task of students is to actively learn and digest, learning management is also very important so that the learning process runs effectively and efficiently in achieving learning objectives such as lesson planning, material mastery, accuracy in using media, strategies, models, learning methods and evaluation techniques.

From the existing problems to provide good competence for students and provide meaningful learning as well as increase student motivation and learning achievement, learning methods are needed that are relevant to the conditions, characteristics, and thinking styles of students of Islamic Religious Education (PAI) Faculty of Tarbiyah and Tadris at IAIN Bengkulu. The learning methods that are expected to overcome these problems are the discussion learning method and the recitation learning method. The discussion method is a teaching method that is closely related to learning to solve problems. The application of the discussion method aims to provide motivation and provide a stimulus to students so that students (reflective thinking). While the recitation method is basically a method in which the lecturer gives assignments so that students carry out learning activities with responsibility and discipline, in doing learning assignments can be done in the classroom or outside the classroom.

In the learning process, there are many factors that affect student performance, including the abilities of the individual. However, not all individuals have the ability to understand the same subject matter, because each student has a different way of understanding the subject matter taught by the lecturer. The difference in the way students obtains, process and process the information they get is called cognitive style. Based on the existing problems, the writer feels the need to conduct research on learning methods and cognitive styles on student achievement. This research is expected to provide an overview for lecturers in developing learning at Islamic Higher Education, especially IAIN Bengkulu, Faculty of Tarbiyah and Tadris, Islamic Religious Education (PAI) study program. The aims of this study were to: 1) examine the effect of the discussion learning method and the recitation method on learning achievement in research methodology courses, 2) examine the effect of independent and dependent cognitive styles on learning achievement in research methodology courses, 3) examine the interaction between learning methods and styles. cognitive on learning achievement of research methodology courses, 4) Testing learning achievement of research methodology courses of students who learn to use discussion learning methods that have a higher dependent cognitive style than those who have independent cognitive styles, 5) Testing of learning achievement of research methodology courses of students who learn to use the recitation learning method that has a higher independent cognitive style than those who have a dependent cognitive style.

2. Method

The research method used is experimental research with a 2×2 factorial research design. The data collection technique used is a test, which consists of a cognitive style test instrument and a learning achievement test instrument. Hypothesis 1, 2, and 3 were tested, using two-way ANOVA analysis (Two Way ANOVA), hypotheses 4 and 5 using t-test (t-test). Prior to the f-test, a prerequisite test for data analysis was carried out in the form of a homogeneity test and a normality test. The subjects of this study were students who took the research methodology course of the Islamic Religious Education (PAI) study program which consisted of 6 (six) classes with a population of 173 students. The population was given a cognitive style test (to determine the

dependent or independent cognitive style), and homogeneity test through an independent sample t test (to measure the same or equivalent ability). A class is said to be homogeneous if the significance value is > 0.05 and a class is said to have a difference if the significance value is < 0.05 . Based on the calculation results, two (2) classes have the same or equivalent abilities, namely: class A and class C, with a significance value of $0.282 > 0.05$ (homogeneity test) and $0.046 < 0.05$ (t-test). The class that was used as the research sample was class A (31 students) and class C (30 students) with a total sample of 61 students. To determine the discussion class and recitation class by means of an intact group by drawing the two classes, the results of the draw were obtained for class A (discussion method) and class B (recitation method).

3. Results and Discussion

After carrying out various tests required of the data obtained from the field, the next step is to test the hypothesis. The hypothesis test conducted is the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable. The method of the influence of independent variables on the dependent variable was analyzed based on an understanding of theoretical concepts. The results of the calculation of the hypothesis test if the significance value is 0.05 , then H_0 is declared rejected and H_a is declared accepted. The results of hypothesis testing 1, 2, 3, and 4, obtained a significant value < 0.05 . From this statement, H_0 is declared rejected and H_a is declared accepted. While in hypothesis 5 the results of the calculation of the hypothesis test obtained a significant value of $0.228 > 0.05$ then H_a is rejected and H_0 is accepted.

The results of this study were concluded: (1) There are differences in learning achievement between students who study the discussion learning method and the recitation learning method, (2) There are differences in learning achievement between students who have dependent and independent cognitive styles in research methodology courses, (3) There is an interaction between learning methods and cognitive styles on learning achievement in research methodology courses, (4) learning achievement in research methodology subjects for students who learn to use discussion learning methods with independent cognitive styles is higher than the dependent cognitive style, (5) learning achievement in methodological subjects research on students who learn to use the recitation learning method with dependent cognitive style there is no difference with independent cognitive style.

4. Conclusion

The results of research and data analysis that have been carried out at the Islamic Religious Education Study Program (PAI) Faculty of Tarbiyah and Tadris concluded: (1) There is an influence of learning methods on learning achievement of research methodology, (2) There is an influence of dependent and independent cognitive style on learning achievement methodology research, (3) There is an interaction between learning methods and cognitive style on learning achievement of research methodology, (4) Learning achievement of research methodology students who learn to use discussion learning methods that have an independent cognitive style is higher than dependent, (5) Methodological learning achievement research on students who learn to use the recitation learning method that has a dependent cognitive style is not higher than the independent cognitive style.

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